

**iMirabilis_2 Expedition (iAtlantic)
Science plan**

31.07.2021-30.08.2021

30 days, start and end in Las Palmas (Spain)

Research Vessel “Sarmiento de Gamboa” (CSIC)

RV Sarmiento de Gamboa (image: Joan Costa, CSIC)

Recommended citation:

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Brief description of the expedition background and aims

Named after the long-lived *Welwitschia mirabilis* plant of western Africa, the iMirabilis_2 expedition is one of the flagship “Demonstrator Capacity Building expeditions” of the iAtlantic project. The expedition will take place on the Spanish Research Vessel *Sarmiento de Gamboa* (SdG) (http://www.utm.csic.es/sarmiento_car.asp) from 31st of Julyth to 30th August 2021, the expedition track and start and end port and dates are display in figure 1 and table 1.

The expedition was originally planned to cover the areas 6 and 9 of iAtlantic, unfortunately the covid 19 situation obligated to cancel the expedition last year and the new schedule does not allow to travel to Namibia and South Africa, therefore, only area 6 will be covered during iMirabilis_2. The ship will travel from Vigo to Las Palmas (Spain) where the expedition will start (Fig. 2). After working in Cabo Verde waters, the ship will move back to Las Palmas where the expedition will finish. Demobilization of large equipment and gear will take place in Vigo.

Fig.1 Map displaying iMirabilis_2 track (red line), departure (Vigo) and arrival port (Las Palmas), and start and end of the expedition (Las Palmas-Las Palmas). In the transit from Vigo to Las Palmas (leg 0), as well as in the expedition (leg 1) capacity building and outreach activities will take place.

Table 1 Main dates of the iMirabilis_2 expedition. Harbours, legs and transits with the corresponding departure, arrival and stay in harbour dates are indicated.

Harbour/Working area	Departure	Arrival	Stay in harbour
Vigo harbour	23/07/2021		16-23/07/2021
Transit Vigo-Las Palmas / EMPEC work (Leg 0)	23/07/2021	29/07/2021	
Las Palmas harbour		30/07/2021	31/07/2021
Las Palmas-Las Palmas (Leg 1)	31/07/2021	30/08/2021	
Transit Las Palmas-Vigo	31/08/2021	04/09/2021	
Vigo harbour	04/09/2021		

Fig.2 Detail of the working areas off Cabo Verde. The green and the yellow box display the locations where the sampling and survey activities will take place. The blue line indicates the contour of the Study Area 6 of iAtlantic.

iMirabilis_2 is an international multidisciplinary expedition with activities contributing to many tasks across iAtlantic’s workpackages. At sea activities will include the study of both the water column (e.g. measuring oceanographic parameters, water and plankton sampling) and the seafloor. iMirabilis_2 mobilises state-of-the-art seabed survey equipment including the Autonomous Underwater vehicle (AUV) Autosub6000 (<https://noc.ac.uk/facilities/marine-autonomous-robotic-systems/autosubs>) and the Remotely Operated Vehicle (ROV) Luso (EMEPC, <https://www.emepc.pt/rov-luso?lang=en>). This advanced technology allows iAtlantic to explore benthic ecosystems in great detail producing large high-resolution photographic results that will be processed automatically using new machine learning approaches. The results of these surveys will be used to produce high resolution habitat maps off Cabo Verde from which scarce information is currently available. Moreover, the ROV Luso will allow collection of selected specimens for taxonomic purposes and for dating. Furthermore, new technologies will be tested during iMirabilis_2 including the eDNA ‘RoCSI’ sampler recently developed by researchers from the National Oceanography Centre (NOC, UK). Seabed lander equipment will also be deployed during iMirabilis_2 to obtain *in situ* information on environmental parameters and demersal deep-sea fish fauna. *Ex situ* experimental work will also take place on the ship, including short-term aquaria experiments with specimens collected with the ROV and incubations of sediment cores, collected by multicore. Beyond the pure research activities, iMirabilis_2 includes detailed training and capacity building components, for instance, researchers from Cabo Verde will join the expedition during the transits to be trained in seabird identification and seabird census techniques. Furthermore, outreach activities are planned during the leg 1 as an expedition member will be fully dedicated to these activities.

Research Vessel Sarmiento de Gamboa

Operator: Unidad de Tecnología Marina (UTM, CSIC)
Country: Spain
Website: <http://www.utm.csic.es/sarmiento.asp>
Vessel Type: Multipurpose Research Vessel
Vessel Class: Global
Scientist berths: 26
Length: 70.5m

Features:

Multidisciplinary research vessel, equipped for oceanography, geology, geophysics, hydrography, and fisheries research. The vessel has several science laboratories on board (250 m²) including a wet lab and a CTD Hangar (55 m²), as well as different freezing storage (50 m²). It is a "quiet" vessel in terms of radiated noise to water. The vessel can operate deep sea ROVs, AUVs, piston corer and large multichannel seismic (6000 m) in addition to fixed scientific equipment on board.

Onboard scientific equipment:

The ship is equipped with an acoustic "gondola" with Multibeam (shallow and deep waters), single beam (hydrographical) and parametric echosounder transducers installed on the lower surface, which provides very high-resolution seafloor mapping and penetration into sub bottom surface respectively. This "gondola" is an "airplane-like" structure mounted on the hull. This structure is separated from the hull avoiding the bubbles produced by the bow of the ship that could affect the acoustic transducers installed on the lower surface. The ship also has two drop keels installed in the middle part of the ship. They can be lowered 3 meters below the keel to separate the transducers installed from the hull, avoiding the acoustic noise produced by water flux and from hull itself.

The complete list of equipment is as follows:

Simrad EA600 (12 / 200 kHz). Hydrography single beam echosounder Installed on gondola
Simrad EK-60 (18 / 38 / 120/ 200 kHz.) Biologic echosounder. Installed on drop keel
Atlas DS (15 kHz). Deep water Multibeam echosounder Installed on gondola.
Atlas MD (50 kHz). Medium / shallow water multibeam echosounder. Installed on gondola.
Atlas P35 (18 kHz). Parametric Subbottom Profiler. Installed on gondola.
RDI 75/150 kHz. ADCP Installed on gondola.
HIPAP. Acoustic Underwater Ultra Short Baseline (USBL) positioning. Installed on gondola.
Scanmar net sensors (Trawl eye / Depth / Catch / Tension / Speed / Distance-Depth) with shipborne transducers installed on drop keel.
CTD, LHPR, SeaSoar from near the surface to depths down to 500 meters while moving at speeds up to 12 knots.

Deck equipment: Cranes and Winches
CTD 8000 m. Coax Ø 11 mm
Plankton sampling 6000 m / Ø 6 mm
Coring 8000 m / Ø 16 mm
Elect. Nets 7000 m / Coax Ø 14 mm

2 x mobile 20 ton trawling Multipurpose Cranes

Aft A- frame

Main crane (12Tons)

Starboard A-Frame

2 x Aux. Cranes

CTD Telescopic Crane.

Sampling devices and instruments in iMirabilis_2

Sampling equipment and analysers on board. Items in black belongs to the vessel and is available on board; **Items in red will be supplied by the researchers; Items in green are the large infrastructures to be used on board: ROV, Autosub, landers.**

Scientists responsible for the gears/equipment are indicated after each item.

Large equipment

- 2 CTD- Rosette. (SBE 911 with TC redundant sensors (3 pairs)+ with rosette (24 bottles, 12 litre each) equipped with a nephelometer (Responsible on board: Ángela Mosquera)
- SBE21 with Turner fluorometer, temperature, conductivity and fluorescence (Responsible on board: Ángela Mosquera)
- QSP-2300 radiance sensor (Responsible on board: Ángela Mosquera)
- Vessel mounted ADCP (Responsible on board: Ángela Mosquera)
- Multibeam echosounder (Responsible on board: Veerle Huvenne)
- Multicorer and extruder (Responsible on board: Andrew Sweetman)
- Box corer (Responsible on board: Andrew Sweetman)
- ROV "Luso" (Responsible on board: Antonio Calado, Cova Orejas, Rui Freitas, Andrea Gori Veerle Huvenne)
- Autosub 6000 (Responsible on board: Daniel Roper, Veerle Huvenne), equipped with EM2040 multibeam echosounder, CTD, downward and oblique forward camera & lights (Responsible on board: Daniel Roper, Veerle Huvenne) and with the new RoCSI eDNA sampler (Responsible on board: Susan Evans)
- 3 landers (1 x benthic respirometer lander, 1 x baited camera lander, 1 x baited trap lander), (Responsible on board: A. Sweetman)

Other equipment

- Two stereomicroscopes (Nikon SMZ 645, Nikon SMZ 1500), cold lights, photocamera adaptable to the stereomicroscope (Nikon DS-FI1) (Responsible on board: Andrea Gori)
- Milli Q (distill water and ultrapure) (Responsible on board: Technicians UTM)
- Fridge +4° C (Responsible on board: Technicians UTM)
- Freezers -80°C y -20°C (Responsible on board: Technicians UTM)
- P15 marine balance (Pols) (Responsible on board: Technicians UTM)
- Oven (Responsible on board: Antonio Calado and Technicians UTM)
- C Node Transponder for subsea positioning system (Responsible on board: Technicians UTM)
- Vacuum pump (Responsible on board: C. Orejas)
- Chillers, pumps, filters, aquaria for maintenance of living organisms on board (Responsible on board: C. Orejas, Andrea Gori)
- Filtration equipment (Responsible on board: Andrea Gori)
- 2 lab incubators (Responsible on board: A. Sweetman)
- Peristaltic pump (Responsible on board: S. Evans)
- Filtration rig for molecular samples (Responsible on board: S. Evans)
- Draga Van Veen (Responsible on board: A. Sweetman)
- WP2 plankton net (Responsible on board: Andrew Sweetman)

Note: After each sampler / instrument I have added one or more researcher who is/are responsible or the contact person for this specific equipment, but for all the equipment and

instruments we will use on board there will be technicians from the UTM (Unidad de Tecnología Marina, CSIC) helping with operation, fine tuning and maintenance. This applies to the equipment supplied by the UTM (in black).

General routine of the expedition¹

As this expedition has multiple tasks and devices requiring different timing, a daily routine cannot be defined, and daily plan will be most probably decided at sea also depending on the meteorological conditions. From the information we have from Cabo Verde it seems the time of the year planned for the leg 1 should be favourable, therefore we expect to have good weather conditions.

- **ROV and Autosub** deployments will take place whenever possible during the day. If several ROV dives take place consecutively, the time between dives can be used to perform **boxcorer** deployments as well as **MUC**, **Van veen Grab** or other “smaller” gears, as the **WP2** plankton net.
- **MB**, **CTD** sampling and maybe **lander deployment** can take place during the night.

Sampling methods

- **Lander/baited cameras/trap deployment.** A total of 5-6 benthic respirometer lander deployments will be undertaken to measure in situ seafloor respiration and nutrient fluxes. Ten baited camera lander deployments will be undertaken to census the scavenging fauna on the abyssal plains. Three to four baited traps deployments will be undertaken to catch deep-sea scavengers to ID fauna from camera images.
- **ROV sampling.** Exploratory ROV transects will be conducted, with some stops when needed to sample benthic organisms, plankton, water and sediment. The ROV is provided with laser pointers, which are necessary to scale the images. The ROV is also equipped with manipulators and a drawer to collect samples in different compartments. The ROV has also Niskin bottles to collect water. More comprehensive information on the Luso ROV will be provided in a separate document. The performance of the ROV transect will be visualised on the 3D bathymetry of the targeted areas which is partially available already. We also intend to use the OFOP software during the expedition. The working bathymetric range will be approximately from ca. 500 to a maximum of 5,000 meters depth.
- **Autosub 6000.** Autosub6000 is the latest 6000 m rated version of the Autosub AUV series, which has been used extensively for ocean science during the last 10 years. The design of the nose and tail sections, including the navigation and control systems, are substantially inherited from the tried and tested Autosub3. The main difference is the depth rating (6000m rather than 1600m), and the energy system (Lithium Polymer rechargeable batteries rather than primary manganese alkaline cells).

¹ Considering the relevance of the roles of the iAtlantic project coordinator (JM. Roberts) as the iMirabilis_2 organiser and principal expedition leader (C. Orejas), as well as their role as the main fundraiser for this expedition, they should be included as last co-authors of the publications produced from this expedition in which they consider they would like to be involved.

With an ultimate range up to 125 km, a maximum operating depth of 6000 m, and a generous payload capacity of 0.5 m³, Autosub6000 is one of the world's most capable deep diving science Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUV).

- **eDNA sampler.** The eDNA sampler is a submersible version of an already existing autonomous sampler which will have a titanium housing and will be pressure tested to 6000 m. It will filter between 35-40 samples (the final number depends on where the sampler is integrated in Autosub) per Autosub dive, with 1 sample every 45 minutes. Between every sample, it is possible to have a cleaning cycle consisting of a bleach flush followed by an ambient seawater flush before the next sample is taken. More comprehensive information on the eDNA samples will be provided in a separate document.
- **CTD-Rosette sampling.** Sampling will be conducted in the before mentioned depth ranges (covering in all cases the depth range of the ROV transects) and the sea surface.
- **Box corer / Van Veen Grab / Multicorer sampling.** Sampling locations will be chosen, if possible, based on the areas explored with the ROV.
- **Multi beam survey.** As the 3D bathymetry for the targeted areas is already available, this information will be used to plan the ROV dives. New MB surveys will be conducted in specific areas to be defined. Further, during the transits we also plan to conduct MB surveys, also needed for capacity building activities.
- **WP2.** Plankton sampling will take place opportunistically.

Important remark: depending on the results obtained during the expedition some of the planned sampling schemes might change and may have to be adapted.

Work program / Contributions of the research teams

Habitat mapping I: Basin-wide and regional bathymetry. GEOMAR bathymetry team

Team lead and members at home: Colin Devey, Anne-Cathrin Wöfl, Mia Schumacher (GEOMAR)

Team lead on board: Veerle Huvenne (NOC)

Background: Seafloor and habitat mapping of marine environments in the Atlantic Ocean.

Aims of your work within the iAtlantic aims, WPs, and tasks:

- Task 2.1 in WP2 - Bathymetry data collection and analysis
- D2.1 Basin-wide Atlantic marine landscape map: Map delineating the different marine environments in the Atlantic Ocean
- MS2.1 State of (bathymetric) mapping in the Atlantic
- MS2.4 Regional habitat maps for the 12 iAtlantic study regions complete
- MS2.5 Updated maps on the state of (bathymetric) mapping in the Atlantic produced

Material & Methods: Multibeam echosounder to map the seafloor and sound-velocity profile (CTD profiler, ROV-CTD or similar) to determine the sound velocity

Tasks and synergies with other iAtlantic teams: WP2 in general as well as WP5's iAtlantic GIS platform

Equipment needed: Multibeam and sound-velocity profile (CTD profiler, ROV-CTD or similar)

Habitat mapping II: Regional and local scale habitat maps. NOC Habitat mapping team

Team members at home: Catherine Wardell, James Strong, Julie Robidart, Dan Jones (NOC)

Team lead and members on board: Veerle Huvenne, Susan Evans (NOC)

Background: Within iAtlantic, the NOC team is working on the development of better approaches to habitat mapping at multiple scales. This work involves new data collection methods (e.g. the development of new sensors and new technologies, such as the eDNA sampler and the Autosub AUV), new data analysis methods that can deal with the vast amounts of data provided by the new sensors and vehicles, and new approaches to data synthesis to produce comprehensive and accurate habitat maps. We aim to apply these new approaches to the Cabo Verde surveys planned for the iMirabilis_2 expedition.

Aims of your work within the iAtlantic aims, WPs, and tasks:

- Habitat mapping work at multiple scales, in particular also the local scale (areas of 1-10km², sub-metre pixel sizes): WP2, T2.2 and T2.3
- Demonstration of the RoCSI eDNA sampler (T2.4.1)
- Machine Learning techniques for automated analysis of large photographic datasets (T2.4.2)

Material & Methods:

1. Habitat mapping at regional scale: application of top-down or bottom-up habitat mapping techniques, based on the combination of environmental data (bathymetry & seabed acoustic backscatter from shipboard multibeam data, seabed (substratum) type information from cores and video, water column characteristics from various CTD devices,...) and faunal data (from video/photography/cores collected over a sufficient number of ground-truthing stations). If biological datasets are limited, top-down techniques such as k-means clustering will be used to map out areas with similar environmental conditions. If sufficient biological data can be obtained, predictive modelling of species occurrences, biodiversity metrics or community characteristics will be applied, using approaches such as Random Forest, GLMs or MaxEnt. The environmental information will enable us to map out the EUNIS habitats in the area, working in a GIS environment. Specific data required: shipboard multibeam bathymetry & backscatter data, CTD data, seabed photographs or video spread over the different types of terrain mapped by the multibeam system (or fauna & substratum information collected by colleagues). Sediment samples for grainsize analysis (or grainsize results provided by colleagues). Voucher specimens to ID unknown species (or IDs provided by colleagues).
2. Habitat mapping at local scale: similar approaches as above, but based on high-resolution data obtained with the AUV and ROV. Data required: AUV-based bathymetry & backscatter map(s). If no multibeam system can be used, we can also use AUV-based sidescan sonar data if needed. Seabed photographs or video, spread over the different benthic habitats/terrains mapped by the AUV (or fauna & substratum information collected by colleagues). Sediment samples for grainsize analysis from the different terrains mapped by the AUV (or grainsize results provided by colleagues).
3. eDNA sampling: The newly developed eDNA sampler from NOC will be integrated into the Autosub6000, and will be used during the iMirabilis_2 expedition. A separate form for the eDNA sampling has been provided. Requirements on the expedition: as many AUV missions with the eDNA sampler as possible, voucher specimens and tissues for DNA barcoding, or barcode data collected by colleagues.

4. **Machine Learning:** The development of Machine Learning algorithms will be tested on extensive photographic datasets obtained with the AUV Grasshopper camera. To assist image annotation, unsupervised machine learning techniques will initially be applied to provide region proposals for the detection of fauna, which reduces the effort required to perform detection manually. These proposals can then be assessed by experts to identify an appropriate taxonomic label. After obtaining sufficient labelled data, supervised machine learning techniques will be used to perform detection and classification simultaneously on the entire dataset. Data required: photograph datasets from AUV missions.

Tasks and synergies with other iAtlantic teams: Hopefully all of the work will be carried out in collaboration with IEO, UEDIN, U. Salento, U. Aveiro among others. E.g. for benthic fauna characterisation from ROV video/photography and AUV photography we would prefer to work with other biological teams as we don't have the capacity to do all the species ID ourselves. Even with the Machine Learning, we will need annotated photographs to help the computers to learn the species characteristics. We also don't have the expertise to identify macrofauna, but the data would be helpful in the habitat mapping and eDNA sequence dataset processing. The eDNA results will be provided to the wider iAtlantic consortium, once the analyses are finished (post-expedition). We will rely on benthic and pelagic species characterisation information (through visual species ID and sequencing of voucher specimens) to inform with eDNA analysis and also valuable metadata collected during the cruise. The Machine Learning work will be carried out in collaboration with GeoMAR (Timm Schoening)

Equipment needed:

Shipboard multibeam system

AUV multibeam, photography, eDNA sampler (RoCSI) and further environmental data (CTD, ADCP, other sensors)

ROV video/photography, sediment sampling, fauna sampling for voucher specimens, if possible also CTD data from ROV; CTD; box- and/or multicore; on board facilities to sample & preserve benthic fauna, and to sub-sample cores

Sufficient computing power and digital storage space

In terms of data storage, we will provide our own (= NOC) back-up disks/QNAP RAID system to copy & store the AUV images, bathymetry & sub-bottom profiler data, together with the Luso photographs and video. Autosub and Luso will have their own as well.

Habitat mapping III: eDNA mapping. RoCSI eDNA sampler team (NOC)

Team lead and members at home: Julie Robidart, Robin Brown, James Wyatt, Chris Cardwell, John Walk, Robyn Samuel (NOC)

Team lead and members on board: Susan Evans, Dan Roper and other Autosub engineers (NOC)

Background: We are currently working on advancing our RoCSI eDNA sampler from technology readiness level (TRL)6 to TRL8. Following the integration of the sampler into Autosub6000, we will deploy and test the integrated RoCSI eDNA sampler in-situ for the first time.

Aims of your work within the iAtlantic aims, WPs, and tasks:

Our work falls into WP2, specifically Task 2.4 advancing the technology readiness level of new mapping technologies and Task 2.4.1 Advance the eDNA sampler for AUV use.

Material & Methods:

We will deploy Autosub6000 with the integrated eDNA sampler off Cabo Verde abyssal plains. Following the habitat mapping conducted at Cabo Verde, we will initially deploy Autosub6000 with the eDNA sampler for an initial short test mission followed by a maximum of 24 hour mission at a time (followed by 24 hours to recharge the battery) where we will filter seawater in the acoustically-mapped region at high resolution.

The Sterivex filters (maximum of 40 per dive) will immediately be collected upon retrieval of Autosub6000 on deck and stored in -80 freezer on board. The filter cartridges will be replaced with sterile filter cartridges for the following dive. Samples will be transported back to the UK on dry ice for subsequent eDNA analysis back in the UK.

In addition, to support data analysis and interpretation we will also take corresponding CTD water samples and collect complementary water/sediment samples using the ROV Luso to further develop an eDNA reference library.

Tasks and synergies with other iAtlantic teams:

The eDNA dataset generated from this will be used for eDNA-based biodiversity assessments in collaboration with partners working in Region 6 (e.g. CNRS), with the habitat mapping team and also the wider iAtlantic consortium.

Equipment needed:

- CTD-rosette to collect water for complementary eDNA analysis.
- -80° C freezer for storage of Sterivex filters from the eDNA sampler.
- MilliQ water
- Approx 1m of bench space near a sink for filtering

Equipment / Spaces supplied from the UTM and Research Vessel:

- Millipore Milli Q Advantage A10 and 2 Millipore Elix 20 destilators
- Milli-Q Advantage A10 Distiller (Millipore)
- Space in the lab (~1-2 m²) for our peristaltic pump and filtration system with access to a power supply and a sink.
- -80° C freezer

Mobile equipment supplied by the UTM

- 2 CTD profilers SEA Bird 911 plus (conductivity sensors, temperature sensors, pressure sensors, oxygen sensors, fluorometers, PAR, transmissometer, altimeter) to acquire in continuum with a 24 bottles (12 L)-rosette
- Freezers (a space of 45 cm (width) x 50 cm (high) x 55 cm (deep) will be needed in the -80°C freezer for storage of Sterivex filters)

Equipment supplied by the researchers and by the iAtlantic project and partners

- Chemicals (RNA later preservative, bleach, ethanol)
- Peristaltic pump and tubing (Cole-Parmer Masterflex L/S)
- 4L and 10L bottles
- 0.22 µm Sterivex filters
- RoCSI
- ROV Luso
- Autosub6000 (NOC)

Palaeoceanography including studies based on foraminifera. UCL and IEO team

Team lead and members at home: David Thornalley (UCL), Irene Perez (IEO)

Team lead on board: Veerle Huvenne (NOC) and Cova Orejas (IEO) will coordinate this activity

Background: Sediment coring of soft sediment sites suitable for paleoceanographic work. We would like to take advantage of any available expedition time, at sites where there is soft sediment on the seafloor, to collect multicores or push core subsamples from box cores.

Aims of you work within the iAtlantic aims, WPs, and tasks: As part of WP3, we are generating paleoceanographic data of decadal-millennial ocean and ecosystem changes at several of the case study sites. Collecting suitable cores from sites within the SE Atlantic would broaden the scope for this work.

Material & Methods: Multicores or push core subsamples from box cores. Extraction of top few cm of core on deck and bagging of sediment; capping and labelling of cores.

Tasks and synergies with other iAtlantic teams: The paleoceanographic work is aimed at complementing the modern physical oceanography of WP1.

Equipment needed:

Multicore and/or box core with plastic tubes. Plastic sample bags.

Space in the wet lab to process the cores (some space in the wet lab. For multicores we would aim to slice one or two tubes into bags. Depending on the core system, we could keep the rest as whole tubes, CTD data probably not necessary. Samples would need to be stored cold, perhaps some frozen.)

Recent foraminifera assemblages analysis (Irene Pérez, IEO)

Foraminifera are found at all depths and in all marine environments. It would be ideal to know the distribution of benthic foraminifera along a depth gradient, and at different environmental conditions, such as different levels of oxygen content or productivity. Understanding the ecological preferences of benthic foraminifera is a valuable insight for the studies that infer ecological conditions and environmental change from subrecent or fossil foraminifera tests. The here proposed research will be conducted if time available, therefore we proposed different sampling schemas depending on the available time. We present those as “best, intermediate and worst case scenarios.

-Best case scenario: sediment samples collected from 0-1 cm depth from multicores or box cores. The volume of sediment should be known. Add Rose Bengal at a concentration of 2 g per litre ethanol >70%. The volume of preservative to be added should at least be equal of the volume of the sample. Samples have to be shaken until an entirely homogeneous mixture is obtained. Replicates from a different deployment of the core should be taken in an ideal scenario.

-Intermediate case scenario: sediment samples collected from 0-1 cm depth from multicores or box cores. The volume of sediment should be known. Add an equal volume of ethanol>70% to the sediment. Samples have to be shaken until an entirely homogeneous mixture is obtained.

-Worst case scenario: a spoon of superficial sediment, preferably from multicores or box cores (grab samplers are not appropriated).

Coral time series. UCL, U. Dalhousie, UEDIN team

Team lead and members at home: Christian Millo (USP, Brazil), David Thornalley (UCL, UK), Owen Sherwood (Dalhousie, Canada), Lea-Anne Henry (Edinburgh, UK), Murray Roberts (Edinburgh, UK)

Team Lead and members on board: Veerle Huvenne (NOC) and Cova Orejas (IEO) will coordinate this activity

Background: Our team aims to take advantage of the iMirabilis_2 expedition to collect coral samples for geochemistry in order to see if we can reconstruct multidecadal or centennial changes in coral growth and the regional oceanography.

Aims of your work within the iAtlantic aims, WPs, and tasks:

This work falls under WP3. The aim of WP3 is to collect and collate timeseries of Atlantic Ocean variability. Cold-water corals offer the opportunity to generate detailed, high-resolution time series of past ocean conditions, essential for understanding the history of the corals' habitats and the history of the ocean itself.

Material & Methods:

Corals will be collected using the ROV Luso. Depending on ROV storage space, corals can be collected opportunistically as part of other sampling dives. Sample sites should reflect the range of water conditions/depths/locations explored during iMirabilis_2 where possible. i.e. priority should be to get a few good samples that cover the whole range, rather than to sample lots of corals from closely spaced locations in similar water.

Specific targets for collection are:

- 1) Primnoids or Bamboo corals. Try to collect large (50cm high or larger) whole colonies, ideally in triplicate from any given site.
- 2) Gold Corals (formerly called "Gerardia"), as well as antipatharians. Same approach as above.
- 3) Scleractinians. Looking for colonies with live growing tips, or large live solitary corals such as *Desmophyllum dianthus*. For colonies, large clumps of about 30cm or bigger, ideally in triplicate from any site. Could be shared with teams doing genetics or reproductive biology.

1 and 2 have priority over 3.

Once collected, Gorgonian corals should be photographed and then frozen. Scleractinia should be photographed, rinsed in freshwater, and dried at room temperature.

Tasks and synergies with other iAtlantic teams:

As mentioned above, depending on the requirements of anyone working on coral genetics or biology, we should be able to arrange to use the skeletal material for geochemistry, if from a large colony or solitary scleractinian.

Equipment needed:

ROV Luso

Freezer

Plastic storage bags (to be supplied)

Coral and other benthic organisms taxonomy. IMAR-UAz, HWU, IEO, FECM/Uni-CV team

Team lead and members at home: Marina Carreiro-Silva (IMAR-UAz), Teresa Amaro (U. Aveiro)

Team lead and members on board: Rui Freitas (UTA), Covadonga Orejas (IEO), Beatriz Vinha (U Salento)

Background: Cabo Verde is part of the Macaronesia biogeographic region together with the Azores, Madeira and Canary Islands. There are putative new coral species identified for Cabo Verde in Sampaio et al (2019) based on museum specimens from the CANCAP and Tyro Mauritania II expeditions that took place between 1976 to 1988. As part of WP2, we would like to confirm the presence of these species at present and compare the cold-water coral fauna and communities in general with the fauna of the Azores to determine the degree of their biogeographic affinity. Further other benthic taxonomical groups will be analysed depending on the available taxonomical expertises.

One of the key objectives of WP4 in iAtlantic is to collect baseline data on natural spatial gradients on ecosystem functional processes of selected deep-sea pelagic and benthic systems under different environmental conditions (e.g. productivity and oxygen conditions). As such, we would like to collaborate on in situ and onboard experiment to determine the ecosystem functioning in terms of oxygen consumption, release of inorganic nutrients and particulate organic carbon by octocorals in Cabo Verde and compare it with the Azores.

Sampaio Í, Carreiro-Silva M, Freiwald A, Menezes G, Grasshoff M (2019) Natural history collections as a basis for sound biodiversity assessments: Plexauridae (Octocorallia, Holaxonia) of the Naturalis CANCAP and Tyro Mauritania II expeditions. *ZooKeys* 870: 1–32.
<https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.870.35285>

Aims of your work within the iAtlantic aims, WPs, and tasks:

- i) Collaborating on habitat mapping and characterization of VMEs in Cabo Verde with WP2. Confirm the presence of new species to Science putatively identified by Sampaio et al (2019) and compare with the Azores, as part of the Macaronesia biogeographic region.
- ii) Collection of specimens to conduct short term experiments on board if possible (in collaboration with IEO) within WP4.
- iii) Participation in outreach activities within WP6 (Portuguese is the official language in Portugal and Cabo Verde).

Aside collaboration with Teresa Amaro (U Aveiro)

Teresa Amaro would be interested in to make the connection between the deep sea and shallow ecosystem in terms of taxonomy, but also in the ecosystem functioning.

Material & Methods:

Undertake video surveys and collection of corals for taxonomic ID validation of ROV images using the ROV Luso (which the IMAR team has used several times in the past).
Onboard experiments using incubation chambers for oxygen and nutrient excretion measurements in a cold room held at 8-15°C, depending of the collection depth for the corals.
In situ ecosystem functioning studies benthic micro-profiling landers and seafloor respirometer landers.

Tasks and synergies with other iAtlantic teams:

Habitat mapping and characterization of benthic communities would be undertaken in collaboration with NOC, IEO and GEOMAR. IMAR has been developing video survey methodologies for seamount areas and has expertise in cold-water coral taxonomy that can contribute to the planned work.

In situ and onboard incubations would be undertaken in collaboration with HWU and IEO. IMAR has experience with aquaria experiments using cold-water corals.

Equipment needed:

- Multibeam
- Millipore Milli Q Advantage A10 and 2 Millipore Elix 20 destilators
- Cool room to maintain alive animals and perform short term experiments
- Milli-Q Advantage A10 Distiller (Millipore)

Mobile equipment supplied by the UTM

- Fridges and freezers
- Stereomicroscope

Equipment supplied by the researchers and by the iAtlantic project and partners

- ROV Luso
- Landers
- Filtration train and vacuum pump (supplied by IEO)
- Diverse material to process benthic samples
- Chemicals (Formaldehyd and ethanol)
- Aquaria, chillers (IEO)

Quantitative video analyses and ecophysiology experiments. IEO, UEDIN, UB, U Salento, Aquarium Finisterrae, FECM/Uni-CV team

Team lead and members at home: Murray Roberts (UEDIN), Patricia Puerta, Cristina Gutiérrez-Zárate, Juancho Movilla, Manuel Hidalgo, Pedro Vélez (IEO), Alfredo Veiga (AquariumFinisterrae), Lea-Anne Henry, Sebastian Hennige, Laurence De Clippele (UEDIN)

Team lead and members on board: Cova Orejas (IEO), Andrea Gori (U Barcelona), Rui Freitas (UTA), Ángela Mosquera (IEO)

Background: the ecological research on benthic deep-sea ecosystems conducted by the teams at the IEO, UEDIN, UB and U. Salento is based on two main approaches. From one side the field/in-situ work conducted by means of ROVs, underwater cameras and ROV, and the oceanographic characterization of the areas, and from the other the experimental work performed in aquaria. These two methodological approaches will allow us to obtain detailed information on the occurrence of Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs), as well as the distribution patterns of key structuring species, as Cold-water corals (CWCs), deep-sea sponges and other ecosystem engineer species that form Marine Animal Forests (MAF *sensu* Rossi et al. 2017). Beside these aspects, underwater video also allows analysis of the population structure of selected conspicuous species as well as growth patterns and habitat formation among others. Complementing this large-scale ecosystem approach, the aquaria experiments tackle the organism level allowing to get insight into the basic biology (e.g. growth, feeding) and physiology of the targeted species, supplying us with valuable information on the vital limits of the species under different environmental situations. Aquaria experiments allow us to investigate the response of the organisms to changes in multiple parameters (e.g. temperature, pH, oxygen, sediment). Our research on board of iMirabilis_2 will include investigations in these two main frames.

Aims of you work within the iAtlantic aims, WPs, and tasks:

The main aims for our work on board are:

1. Map the benthic ecosystems around Cabo Verde (ROV Luso and AutoSub) in close collaboration with the mapping teams of GEOMAR and NOC. We will explore options to

2. use new automated mapping approaches to create image datasets suitable for iAtlantic machine learning-based analysis planned in WP2, and as a capacity building activity in WP6.
3. Analyses of coral and gorgonians species distribution patterns, population structure and growth from the video material recorded in Cabo Verde. This work will be conducted as a collaborative research between IEO, NOC, UEDIN and U. Salento. Whenever possible other species from other taxa will be also analysed. Growth analyses and assessment of the dead/living part of the scleractinian reefs will be also conducted in collaboration between IEO, UEDIN and Marum. Specimens will be also collected by means of the ROV manipulator for taxonomical purposes. This part of the work will be done in collaboration between IEO and IMAR.
4. Sampling of specimens by ROV manipulator for analyses of the community trophic structure through stable isotope analyses, as well as fatty acids. This work has been started in a previous expedition (ANNA 2016, METEOR) in collaboration with several partners involved in that expedition, with Marum the lead. This work will be conducted by IEO, UEDIN, University of Barcelona, Marum, U Salento and other partners.
5. Short term experiments will be conducted on board to obtain the first data on the feeding biology (e.g. capture rates) of selected CWC species (gorgonians as well as scleractinians or hydroids could be targeted).
6. Sampling for taxonomic identification including description of new species. Target groups include cold-water corals and sponges, notably the stylasterids (Alberto Lindner, UFES), black corals (Tina Molotsdova, Dennis Opresko), hydroids (Lea-Anne Henry, UEDIN), gorgonians (Iris Sampaio, Marina Carreiro-Silva, IMAR-UAz, Andrea Gori, UB), seapens (Louis Allcock, NUI), sponges (Joana Xavier, CIIMAR), holoturians (Teresa Amaro). Other experts will be involved.

Our work will contribute to the following WPs: WP2, 3, 4, 5 and 6, and specifically to the following tasks:

WP1

Task 1.5 Conduct genomic analyses. iMirabilis_2 will gather VME indicator species with wide Atlantic distribution for gene flow estimation in WP1.

WP2

Task 2.2 Regional-scale mapping in iAtlantic's 12 regions (100-1000 km).

Task 2.3 Local scale habitat mapping (1-10s km).

We will contribute with mapping of region 6.

Task 2.5 Analysis of spatial patterns in ecosystem drivers.

We will contribute with mapping of region 6.

WP3

Task 3.3 Analyse and report on drivers of ecosystem change and tipping points over centennial to millennial timescales.

We will contribute collecting specimens and sediment samples.

WP4

Task 4.2 Compare natural spatial gradients in deep pelagic and benthic ecosystem functioning. Base line information will be obtained from selected species. Short term experiments will be conducted on board.

Task 4.3 Conduct ex situ single and multiple stressor experiments on hard-bottom VME species

Base line information will be obtained from selected species. Short term experiments will be conducted on board. Video analysis of live and dead regions of the coral habitat to assess habitat structure.

WP5

Task 5.2 Development of iAtlantic advanced web-based GIS-tools.

We will contribute supplying with information on functional features of selected species (e.g. physiological performance of selected species, physiological limits).

WP6

Task 6.3 Outreach and dissemination

Activities will be conducted on line and in harbours (see specific text “Outreach and capacity building activities” later in this document)

Task 6.5 Capacity building

Several training activities will be conducted on board in collaboration with several teams (see specific text “Outreach and capacity building activities” later in this document)

Material & Methods:

Video processing will be conducted in the home labs following diverse methodologies we have been used and successfully applied in several publications (e.g. Orejas et al. 2009, 2016; Gori et al. 2013; Vad et al. 2017). On board annotations, probably using the OFOP software, will be carry on obtaining a first analyses of the transects.

The video records corresponding to the way down and up from the ROV will be also recorded as this video material if of interest from Henk-Jan Hoving (GEOMAR) to characterise the gelatinous zooplankton across the water column.

Photo processing from Autosub6000 will be conducted mostly by GEOMAR and NOC and our teams (IEO, UEDIN, UB and U Salento) will collaborate in this task.

Specimens for stable isotope analyses will be collected with the ROV manipulators.

Aquaria experiments will be conducted using the experimental chambers we have been using in previous investigations (e.g. Tsounis et al. 2010, Gori et al. 2015).

Results of the granulometric and POC content of sediment cores will be needed to complement several of the investigations mentioned above.

Tasks and synergies with other iAtlantic teams:

As in any multidisciplinary research expedition, several aspects tackled from other research teams will be of interest for our teams. Among those it can be highlighted:

- The mapping activities will be performed in collaboration with GEOMAR and NOC.
- The oceanographic information will be also a basic tool for the ecological work to be conducted in iMirabilis_2.
- The machine learning methods to be applied by GEOMAR are of high interest for us and we would like to collaborate in this part of the work.

Equipment needed:

Equipment / Spaces supplied from the UTM and Research Vessel:

- Multibeam
- Millipore Milli Q Advantage A10 and 2 Millipore Elix 20 destilators
- Cool room to maintain alive animals and perform short term experiments
- Vacuum pump WP6122050 (Millipore)
- Milli-Q Advantage A10 Distiller (Millipore)

Mobile equipment supplied by the UTM

- Box corer (if possible, with several boxes)

- 2 CTD profilers SEA Bird 911 plus (conductivity sensors, temperature sensors, pressure sensors, oxygen sensors, fluorometers, PAR, transmissometer, altimeter) to acquire in continuum with 24 bottles (12 L) rosette
- Fridges and freezers

Equipment supplied by the researchers and by the iAtlantic project and partners

- ROV Luso
- AUV Autosub6000
- Filtration train and vacuum pump (IEO)
- Diverse material to process benthic samples
- Chemicals (Formaldehyd and ethanol)
- Aquaria, chillers (IEO, U Barcelona, A.Finisterrae-TBC)
- Hard discs to save the video material recorded with the Luso (IEO)

Spaces needed:

- Space in dry lab
- Space in cool room to perform experiments
- Space in chemical lab

Material we will supply:

- Experimental chambers
- Oxygen sensor
- Thermoplate for incubations
- OFOP software

De Clippele L, Gafeira J, Robert K, Hennige S, Lavaleye M, Duineveld GCA, Huvenne VAI, Roberts JM (2017) Using novel acoustic and visual mapping tools to predict the small-scale spatial distribution of live biogenic reef framework in cold-water coral habitats. *Coral Reefs* 36: 255–268

Benthic ecosystem functioning. HWU team

Team lead and members on board: Andrew Sweetman (HWU), Danielle de Jonge (HWU), Daniela Yepes (UFES PhD student)

Background: Studying biodiversity and ecosystem processes in different ecosystem settings/ across environmental gradients (i.e., space-for-time substitutions) can provide an indication of how ecosystems will respond to anthropogenic changes in environmental variables. iAtlantic is going to make use of this approach to provide baseline information about pelagic and benthic biodiversity and ecosystem functioning in different deep-sea regions of the Atlantic and facilitate an assessment of how climate-mediated changes in specific environmental variables (e.g., changes in POC flux) may influence pelagic and benthic ecosystems in the Atlantic Ocean in future. Target ecosystems for baseline / environmental gradient studies will include bathyal and abyssal ecosystems underlying eutrophic and more oligotrophic water masses where POC fluxes range from <0.5 to $2-3 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$. Selection of such areas will allow an assessment of how predicted declining POC flux will alter benthic ecosystems. The iMirabilis_2 expedition to the Cabo Verde Abyssal Plain will allow us to assess the benthic and pelagic biodiversity in the area, and test how benthic ecosystems are functioning naturally in an oligotrophic environment. This data will then be compared to similar data sets from more eutrophic environments such as the Porcupine Abyssal Plain which will allow us to begin to understand how declining POC flux from climate change will influence deep-sea benthic environments, thereby feeding in information to iAtlantic WP4.2. The expedition will also allow us to sample seafloor sediments from upper bathyal depths with a multicore and test the effect of ocean

warming and changing food supply on benthic processes from shipboard experiments (iAtlantic WP4.4).

Aims within the iAtlantic aims, WPs, and tasks:

The work that we will do will be primarily to partly complete tasks WP4.2 and 4.4 in iAtlantic. Our main goals will be to undertake 10 replicate baited camera deployments and fish trap experiments (n= 3-4) to catalogue abyssal scavenger diversity and document scavenger

activities, and abundances (WP4.2). The baited camera deployments will each last 24 hrs in total and the baited trap experiments will last 48 hrs. We will also sample nekton using bongo nets at random opportunistic locations to collect fauna for isotope signatures to elucidate pelagic trophic structure. A total of 6 benthic respirometer experiments will be run in the westernmost abyssal region as well. We will use this instrument to measure seafloor respiration, CO₂ production, nutrient fluxes and measure C flow through the benthic food web in each respirometer chamber. Each lander deployment will be 48 hrs in duration. The data from this work will feed into WP4.2. We will make 6 MUC corer deployments to sample sediment from <1000m on the Cabo Verde slope to do ex situ shipboard experiments. These experiments will be used to assess how seafloor communities respond to warming ocean temperatures and declining POC quality, which will result from shifts from fast sinking diatoms to slow sinking picoplankton as oceans warm. This work will be run in collaboration with colleagues from UFES in Brazil (Dr. Angelo Bernadino) and feed data into WP4.4.

Material & Methods:

We will base our work around the use of a baited camera lander, baited trap, and respirometer lander for WP4.2. Baited cameras will document bait attending fauna, their abundance and scavenging rates with trap-caught specimens providing voucher specimens to ID the fauna observed in camera footage. The respirometer lander will quantify changes in respiration (O₂ consumption, CO₂ production) and nutrient fluxes in benthic chambers. C-flow through the benthic food web will be quantified from isotopically labelled algal and bicarbonate tracers that will be injected into the chambers at the seafloor at the start of the experiment, and its incorporation into microbes and fauna quantified over 48 hrs. The work for WP4.4 will require the use of a MUC to sample bathyal sediments. These sediments will be incubated in cores in incubators set at different temperatures onboard the ship to assess how seafloor ecosystems respond to seafloor warming and altered POC inputs due to climate change.

Tasks and synergies with other iAtlantic teams:

Data from these seafloor surveys and experiments will feed into WP5 of iAtlantic.

Equipment needed:

MUC, pinger required to locate seafloor during each MUC deployment (supplied by Paulo Sumida), filtered cold seawater (around 100 L), lab space for shipboard experiments. Multibeam, Milli Q water, Use of the "fridge room" to incubate sediment cores at 1 to 4°C, P15 marine balance, Fridges and freezers, Bongo Net, Multicorer, CTD to collect water samples.

Equipment / Spaces supplied from the UTM and Research Vessel:

- Millipore Milli Q Advantage A10 and 2 Millipore Elix 20 destilators
- Use of the "fridge room" to incubate sediment cores at 1 to 4°C
- P15 marine balance (Pols)
- Milli-Q Advantage A10 Distiller (Millipore)
- Quick release to release landers from crane wire at the sea surface
- Filtered seawater will be needed

Mobile equipment supplied by the UTM

- 2 CTD profilers SEA Bird 911 plus (conductivity sensors, temperature sensors, pressure sensors, oxygen sensors, fluorometers, PAR, transmissometer, altimeter) to acquire in continuum with a 24 bottles (12 L) rosette
- Fridges and freezers
- Multicorer, with multiple spare tubes (10cm diameter) and spare parts for multicorer

Equipment supplied by the researchers and by the iAtlantic project and partners

- Landers (Leg 1) (1 x benthic respirometer lander, 1 x baited camera lander, 1 x baited trap and mooring floats and line)
- Filtration system
- 2 x core Incubators
- WP2 net

Outreach and capacity building activities I. Sea scape team

Team lead and members at home: Vikki Gunn (Seascope), Laurence De Clippele (UEDIN)

Team lead and members on board: Kelsey Archer Barnhill (UEDIN), Beatriz Vinha (U Salento/IEO/NOC) + others?

Leg 0 (Transit Vigo-Las Palmas) and Leg 1 (Las Palmas-Cabo Verde-Las Palmas)

Aims of your work within the iAtlantic aims, WPs, and tasks:

Activities will contribute to Task 6.3 (outreach and dissemination) and Task 6.5 (capacity building) with perhaps some contribution to Task 6.5 (stakeholder engagement).

Material & Methods:

We will work up a communications plan for the expedition once everything is a bit more concrete. We will also develop a suite of general project materials (brochures, banners, etc) that can be used during port calls etc. A pre-cruise webinar will set the scene for the wider consortium, focusing in particular on what the Fellows will be doing during the cruise. Kelsey will be on board specifically as an outreach person, so she will be responsible for sending most of the on-board outreach material back to shore. We should also not miss the opportunity to get some good imagery and footage during the expedition itself – UEDIN and/or Seascope can provide AV equipment. We'll also develop a good web presence around the expedition in advance of it leaving, and to support the press releases etc that we put out (see below).

Port call activities: The extent to which we can do local outreach in connection with the port calls depends on the level of COVID-19 restrictions in place at the time. We will need to liaise with the ship operator and port authorities before we can really plan activities for the port calls – some ports will not allow public access which will restrict what we can do, and it may be that we won't know what might be possible until quite close to the date. In any case, we'll have some materials pre-prepared.

Expedition blog: Kelsey will be the main person writing the expedition blog, but others may wish to contribute too (which we would encourage). VG will set up a project-wide expedition blog platform and take care of receiving materials and posting the blogs online (easier than uploading directly from the ship). Depending on internet connectivity, we could look to schedule some live Q&A sessions with the teams on board. We can also do some basic training so that people on board can shot short video clips and interviews, if time permits (I know the science legs will be very busy, but some short clips would be great for social media).

Expedition leadership and preparation: We have talked previously about using this expedition as an opportunity for 1-2 young researchers per leg to shadow the PI and learn how to run an expedition. The pre-expedition preparations and mobilisation are also an important learning opportunity so we should see how we can maximise this (GEOMAR previously voiced an interest in doing something on this, perhaps not specifically in relation to this expedition).

Wider capacity building: We need to be mindful to maximise training opportunities, by filming short “how to” or demonstrations guides on board, or by using photos to develop other resources. We will explore whether a “buddy” system can be set up between those on board and those back in land (especially for South Atlantic participants who have missed out on berths).

For the rest of the WP6 activities, easier to break this down leg by leg:

- 1) Port call (1) in Vigo:** This is the start of the whole expedition so we should capitalise on this and see what engagement we can get with European press and media in Vigo before the ship departs. It will be an easier sell for groups like EuroNews to get them to come and film in Vigo as the ship leaves, rather than pitching for them to come to Cabo Verde. Murray has expressed an interest in making a visit to the ship at either the start or end of the expedition, depending on travel restrictions. We should certainly have a press release ready for the start of the expedition that can be circulated to all interested partners to use with their own institutional communications teams, and well as a wrap-up statement ready at the end of the cruise.
- 2) Leg 0 (Transit Vigo-Las Palmas)** ROV training activities and SeaBird Census and identification training will be conducted during the transit leg 0, from Vigo to Las Palmas. Researchers from Cabo Verde and Portugal will be involved as trainees. Training will be in charge of the Luso ROV team and Ornithologist from the University of Barcelona.
- 3) Port call (2) Las Palmas:** Depending on CoVID restrictions, engage with local contacts in Las Palmas to see if what activities might be possible/desirable (e.g., short presentations, perhaps invite some local VIPs etc). WP6 can support by providing materials etc, liaising with local contacts, helping with logistics etc.
- 4) Leg 1 (Las Palmas - Las Palmas):** WP6 activities will centre on the blog and any live online sessions that might be possible. There are limited spaces for students (already allocated), but we should be mindful that there will be learning opportunities on board for many people, which we need to identify and record. Kelsey will be pivotal in helping with this, with support from the land-based team.

This port call should focus on highlighting the science achieved during the expedition, and we should plan appropriate activities around that. Potential to engage with press etc – we have now Rui Freitas involved in the Leg 1 and Jacob has also local contacts. Also see above about Murray potentially coming out, but I think this might be better done in Vigo at the start (less travel).

Tasks and synergies with other iAtlantic teams:

- Björn Fiedler and Henk-Jan Hoving (GEOMAR), Teresa Amaro (U. Aveiro), and Jacob González-Solís (UB), as well as Rui Freitas (University of Cabo Verde) for local Cabo Verde contacts
- Need to identify any iAtlantic fellows on board (Beatriz Vinha, Danielle de Jonge, Daniela Yepes, Ángela Mosquera, Kelsey Archer Barnhill and Susan Evans)
- Vikki Gunn (Seascope) will develop the expedition communications plan with input and support from IEO and UEDIN

Equipment needed:

We will need a decent internet connection – as a basic requirement to be able to email text and photos off the ship, but preferably good enough to also send video – and if possible good enough to do live online broadcasts from the ship.

VG or UEDIN will provide a camera and sound recording equipment to take footage on the ship. Pre-cruise AV training can be arranged if necessary. Ask Veerle about whether the NOC drone could be used (only possible if there is a qualified operator on board)

Complementary activities to be conducted if time available

CTD Sampling in GEOMAR CVOO Station, MB Data from areas shallower than 300 meters (Responsible: Björn Fiedler)

If time available a CTD cast will be conducted in the GEOMAR CVOO Station.

Björn is mainly interested in the CVOO sampling. Both for bgc samplings but also for zooplankton sampling. But he would be also happy if it would be just a CTD cast without any sampling. Other opportunistic samplings in other areas are not of primary interest for him.

The team from B. Fiedler will be also interested in any multibeam data from regions shallower than 300 m (up to very shallow waters). Background is the recently purchase of a small ROV which is capable of diving down to 300 m, incl. a small manipulator and a USBL System (<http://www.teledynemarine.com/vlbv300>). Cabo Verde researchers will use it for near coastal or seamount surveys, but they are lacking high-res bathymetric maps near the coast. Hence, any opportunistic data from these water depths are highly welcomed. A target region is around Santa Luzia but data from any other region would be great to have as well.

Sediment sampling for eDNA from cephalopods, jellies and fish (Responsible: Henk-Jan Hoving)

Henk-Jan is interested in eDNA from cephalopods, jellies and fish, and to detect eDNA with pelagic origin in sediments.

He would be interested in any MUC from the deep sea in Cabo Verde.

Henk-Jan is in contact with Andrew Sweetman and Susan Evans to discuss possibilities on collection of eDNA.

Transit Vigo-Las Palmas (Leg 0)

Seabird Ecology. Outreach and capacity building activities II. U Barcelona, Sotavento, Projecto Vito team.

Team lead and members at home: Jacob González-Solís (team leader and trainer; Professor at the University of Barcelona), Teresa Militão/Mariona Sardà (coordinators of the Sotavento team in the MAVA seabird project), Evandra Gomes (technician from “Projecto Vito”), Carla Lopes (technician from “Projecto Vito”)

Team lead and members on board: Joan Carles Abella (Independent Researcher), Herculano Dinis and Nadito Barbosa (Projecto Vito)

Background: Our team have been conducting research on seabird biology and conservation in Cabo Verde over the last 15 years. Over the last 3 years we have been involved in a project

funded by MAVA foundation to develop a number of strategies aimed to improve seabird conservation in Cabo Verde, including:

1. Research and capacity building
2. National Action Plan for Seabird Conservation
3. Effective protection of all priority seabird colonies
4. Building public awareness and engagement for seabirds
5. Improving the legal framework and enforcement capacity

Over the next three years, we will be involved in a second phase of the same project. In this context, the transit from Vigo to Las Palmas will be a unique opportunity to contribute to some of the strategies mentioned above, in particular, in terms of capacity building in seabird censusing/monitoring and building public awareness and engagement for seabirds.

Aims of your work within the iAtlantic aims, WPs, and tasks:

In these transits, we expect to

- (1) train 2 technicians, already involved in the project and mostly from Cabo Verde, in seabird identification and censusing skills.
- (2) contribute increasing public awareness and engagement for seabirds in Cabo Verde, through a number of outreach activities among the local population, before and after the transit; Specifically it will be interesting to promote these activities in the context of the second phase of the Cape Verde Seabird Conservation Project, where the dissemination of the cruising activities can be included.
- (3) Obtain valuable data on the distribution and abundance of seabirds and other marine megafauna over the sampled areas and produce a report available upon request.

Material & Methods:

The method of seabird censusing will be mostly based on the article by Tasker et al. 1984 and widely accepted as the standard method for seabird censusing at sea and it is also the basic method used to feed the European Seabirds At Sea (ESAS) Database. This method allows determining absolute seabird densities (birds/km²) as well as for other marine megafauna. The method suffers from a number of potential biases, and therefore results must be used with caution, but it is currently considered the easiest and most rigorous method for this type of censuses during ship transits allowing to compare data across different areas and periods.

Tasker M, Jones PH, Dixon T, Blake BF (1984) Counting seabirds at sea from ships: a review of methods employed and a suggestion for a standardized approach. *Auk* 101:567-577

Tasks and synergies with other iAtlantic teams:

Would be very interesting to share transits with marine mammal experts as well as other seabird experts to learn from them too.

Equipment needed:

No special needs from ship equipment. We would bring our own equipment for watching and photographing seabirds and marine megafauna in general.

Participants list

Leg 0. Transit Vigo-Las Palmas (23.07-30.07.2021)

	Expertise	Name	email	Institution
1	Geology. Cruise leader	Pedro Madureira	Pedro.madureira@emepc.mm.gov.pt	EMEPC
2	Benthic biology/ROV trainee iAtlantic	Beatriz Vinha*	beatrizvinha95@gmail.com	University of Salento/IEO/NOC
3	Seabird ecology / trainer iAtlantic	Joan Carles Abella*	otusco@gmail.com	Free lance
4	Seabird ecology /trainee iAtlantic	Herculano de Andrade Dinis*	projectovito.director@gmail.com	Projectovito
5	Seabird ecology / trainee iAtlantic	Nadito Jesus Pina Barbosa*	naditojesuspina Barbosa@gmail.com	Projectovito
6	Outreach	Kelsey Barnhill*	kelsey.barnhill@ed.ac.uk	UEDIN
7	UTM technicians	UTM IT		UTM-CSIC
8	UTM technicians	UTM MB		UTM-CSIC
9	ROV technicians-Team Responsible	António Calado	apgcalado@emepc-portugal.org	EMEPC
10	ROV technicians	Andreia Afonso	aafonso@emepc-portugal.org	EMEPC
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